

Development of Creativity in A Child Is- An Important Factor in The Upbringing of a Child

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Abstract

The article highlights the need for early educational reform and the formation of "human capital" to identify the child's abilities early, to teach creativity and creativity based on knowledge, one of the important factors in raising a child is the development of creative abilities thought about the formation of social tasks associated. From the growing youth, the task is not only to create all the necessary conditions for ensuring their right to education.

Keywords: Creativity, ability, fine arts, painting, intellectual, cleverness, intelligence, intellect, mind, artist, creative thinking, creative potential, intellectual potential, individual, virtue,

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By the 21st century, the requirements imposed on the world education system are being reorganized in a way that is inextricably linked with the factor of "human capital" and the social tasks associated with its formation. From the growing youth, the task is not only to create all the necessary conditions for ensuring their right to education, but also to educate the future generation from within which modern societies are capable of ensuring the process of drastic economic growth, new technological directions of today's development, the future development of a numbered society. Therefore, today's public education system should consist of the process of cultivating unique talents. To do this, since childhood, the development of skills, in particular, artistic-aesthetic imagination, creativeness and creativity, which provide for the development of visual growth, is required. The emergence and introduction of new ideas into practice are inextricably linked with ensuring the creativity of the child, and the development of creativity in schoolchildren is one of the most pressing pedagogical problems of our time.

The problem of creating new, original and high-level platforms, such as Facebook, Google, Instagram, Telegram, etc., which did not exist before, and whose social needs were very high in ensuring economic growth on the issue of creativity around the world, has been viewed from the point of view of the problem of inviting them to the world market and radically changing the life. The ability and ability to create innovation are valued as national wealth. And on the basis of the creation of innovation, it becomes clear that ensuring the creativity of the child remains the same. Therefore, on the basis of creativity, being able to predict the result and the result in advance, being able to properly organize the production process, combining all around its own idea, is evaluating society as the negation of taking the situation from one state to another. Accordingly, the main content of education today is determined by the fact that it consists not only in the acquisition of certain knowledge, skills and abilities, but also in the creation of a person with an ethic-aesthetic imagination, observability, cognition of the essence, finding a solution to complex situations, creative potential. And in this it is important to have creativity, imagination, fantasy, artistic thinking.

The reform process of today's school education in Uzbekistan is also undergoing radical changes. The concept of development of the system of public education until 2030 was adopted. According to him, in addition to raising the moral and moral development of the growing younger generation to a new level, introducing innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process, qualitative updating of the content of the continuous education system, applying the principles of individualization to the educational process, the need for purposeful development of creativity skills in students was also identified.

And in the development of creativity, the importance of fine art samples, drawing skills is very high.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan M.PF-4947 of Mirziyoyev on February 7, 2017"on the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PF-5538 of September 5, 2018"on additional measures for improvement of the system of management of Public Education", PF-5712 of April 29, 2019"on approval of the concept of development of the system of public education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers dated September 30, 2017 № pp-3304 "on measures for the further improvement of the system of training of pedagogical personnel, retraining of personnel of public education and their professional development", decree № PP-3289 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated September 26, 2017, serves to a certain extent this research work in the implementation of the tasks.

Various pedagogical aspects of the problem of ensuring and developing creativity in students have interested scientists from the earliest times. In the structure of ancient Greek, Chinese, Indian, zardushtian educational beliefs, the Islamic educational code, the development of creativity in the system of national pedagogical views and the creation of its opportunities were discussed. The problems of creativity has been studied in such disciplines as Philosophy, Sociology, Political Science, Economics, Management, advertising, culture, art, marketing, Informatics, pedagogy and psychology. Since the last century, the possibilities of creativity began to be widely studied. Theories of creativity were created and widely introduced into practice, the following system of views was formed:

philosophy of social importance and necessity of art, basics of aesthetics and Art Studies (M.N.Y.Afasiyev, V.P.Bransky, G.Velflin, B.R.Vipper, N.N.Y.Volkov, G.- G.Gadamer, G.Grem, S.M.Daniel, M.S.Kagan, V.V.Kandinsky, P.A.Godin, Yo.M.Latman, Yo.V.Down, B.A.Uspensky, V.A. Favorsky, P.A.Florensky, U.Eco and so on.)

art and its psychology, art pedagogy, pedagogical bases of creativity, theories of creativity and intellectual attachment (D.N.Y.Abramyan, V.M.Allaxverdov, R.Arnhelm, L.S.Vigotsky, J.Gilford, A.N.Y.Leontyev, B.S.Meylax, A.Menegetga, A.Asborn, S.L.Rubinshteyn, P.V.Simonov, R.B.Haikin, G.M.Fers, Z.Freud, K.- G.Yung, P.N.Y. Yakobson and so on.);

creativity development pedagogy and mental cards (G.S.Altshuller, A.V.Gudryavsev, Tani Byuzen, Edvar de Bana, Bab Eberle, A.V.Bakushinsky, S.D.Levin, B.M.Nemensky, B.A.Stolyarov, N.N.Y.Famine, V.S.Sherbakov, B.P.Device v.the b.);

emotional-empirical, sensor training basics, step-by-step theories in mental development (Jean Piage, Paul Kleinman, M.Montesorri, F.Frebel, A.Decrali, V.Davidov, A.Z.Zek, A.P.Usova).

Cognitive theories of creativity (George Kelly), psychoanalytic theories (Z.Freud, K.Yung), compensation theory (A.Adler, Frost Fromm, Relo Mey, Abraham Maslow), theories on the fact that creativity is an activity based on the shell of an active creation (D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya, N.V.Drujin, Eat.A.Ponamarov) developed.

Dedicated to the discussion of various aspects of General school education in Uzbekistan A.Musurmonova, M.Quronov,S.Nishanova, N.Jo' rayev, A.Begmatov, M.Makhmudova, B.Shermuhamedov, K.Riskulova, R.Mevlonova, O.Khasanboeva, I.Valikho'jayeve, P.Yusupova, O.Jamoliddinova, G.Qosimova, R.Safarova, A.Bekmuradov, M.Haydarav scientists as Nazarova ensured the development of the field of research.

The issue of education and its systematization in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the factors determining the national strategy. In the years of independence, the issue of education was recognized as one of the most priority areas, and its goal was to create a "harmonious personality". Today, however, the purpose of the educational system is changing in relation to the individual and his country's economy and strategic development, and is oriented to the concept of "human capital", which provides for the development of the country's prospects.

At first, such important issues as radical reform of education before the educational system, nationalization of the content of education, the construction of its foundations on the basis of democratic principles and national interests, the liberation of the content of education from ideology, bringing it to the level of world standards were established, now the second radical process in the educational system has begun, These new developments are inextricably linked with the principles of creating a new Uzbekistan in the country's strategy. These fundamental changes focus on education as "human capital", that is, on the education system capable of implementing technological revolutions in the country's economy, delivering human resources for economic growth and development, and, in essence, training personnel aimed at a new type of economic efficiency.

Today, a new period of educational reforms has begun in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the purpose of these radical changes is determined by several factors:

the fact that the state of the national education system is lagging behind the modern requirements of today's world, the world economy is developing at a

rapid pace, the country needs to implement its plans for the near and far future in order to be included in the ranks of these advanced countries;

the potential and direction of the world economy is changing, the world market in the last period was characterized by the presence of individual individuals with creative abilities on the basis of new innovative goods (Facebook, mobile phone and communication, telegram, computers, mobile communication, communication without means), these individual people are changing the mentality of the whole country and the world and are;

if at first the education of a free and harmonious person was enough for the development of the state, then today there is a free creative, a leader capable of manifesting creativity, that is, a leader capable of uniting new people around him, an increasing demand for a productive leader;

if at first there was intellectual growth and development, that is, creativeness is needed today, that is, individuals who have formed their own thinking on the basis of creativity and have taken this creativeness in the direction of serving for economic growth;

the fact that there may be different talents in a person, here are the first values in a child on the basis of these talents, the creativeness factor plays an important role, the creativeness characteristics are extremely necessary for our society and it is necessary to form this characteristic from early childhood, but in our national education system it is customary to form;

the issue of new educational reforms is that our country is inextricably linked with its close and long-term goals, but it is necessary to organize critical review and re-awareness processes in relation to the existing system in order to ensure this process;

we all want the child to have a great talent, but there are dozens of issues that we need to recognize the need to develop simple creativity, artistic thinking to the child in order to make this goal Real in a concrete family, concrete school environment, and today we should not ignore them.

Consequently, today's educational reforms and the goal of the formation of the "human capital" demonstrate the need for us to teach the child the characteristics of creativity and creativity on the basis of knowledge of his dignity very early. So, one of the important factors in the upbringing of a child is the development of the dignity of creativity in this child, and here is an example from the creation of a free creative personality on this basis.

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